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EUROPEAN ENVIRONMENTS:

HOW A NEW CLIMATE IS CHANGING THE OLD WORLD

Student Name: Flavia Curatolo

Home University: Deusto Spain

Host University: Groningen The Netherlands

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Introduction :

In an ever changing world made of climate, social and political weathers so drastically different from one another some basic things never change. One of them is for example the fact that we all need food for our survival. Yet, still a small amount of people ask themselves how we can get our food everyday on the table. It is by asking ourselves about the simple things that are in our everyday lives that the responses may lie to face what is the biggest catastrophe of human kind: global change and it's numerous consequences. My generation and future ones will have to deal with this ongoing problem that no one wanted to face seriously. The consequences of the environmental crisis are faced more or less on the same intensity in all parts of the world since we are living in a world that is interconnected because of the globalization. Decisions that have been taken in one part of the planet have consequences locally in another part of the world. We are one with the earth, it feeds us gives us life and in return we might have to start to acknowledge this more seriously and show some respect. The importance of interconnectedness is also something that we might want to think about and get out of our "individual bubble". It is about getting in touch with our environment and changing the perspective. Begin to acknowledge that there is also a peripheral vision and not just what is seen forwards, in the immediate view. It is not because we do not see the consequences directly that they do not exist. Every action has a reaction.

75% of the food is consumed in urban areas in an European context. So it is relevant to look into the perspective of who consumes, produces and the way they see it. In a larger scale the European Union wants to be the "guardian angel" of the environment and sustainability issues. One of the 2020 goals is to produce food and transport it in a more sustainable way.¹ Nonetheless, are there real changes being made? Maybe it is time to really change the way food is viewed and to start developing an alternative way of consuming and regarding it. Another way, to view , produce and consume is possible indeed. In this paper what the focus will be about is on the urban vegetable gardens in the city of Groningen in The Netherlands. New civil spaces are being created. An emergence of public memory, traditions, resilience and environmental (not only soil related) but also in the sense of community is being developed. Talking to some activists and interviewing them since they are being the change will be relevant

¹http://ec.europa.eu/research/agriculture/scar/pdf/scar_feg3_final_report_01_02_2011.pdf

to know what they think and feel about the environment and their activities. It will also allow to answer or give some answers if urban vegetable gardens contribute and reflect sustainability and community building in Groningen? And if this model may be exported somewhere else in the world? We have all heard the statement “from a local action to a global one” do these activists really think they are part of a movement? Or are they just a “drop in the ocean”? The way that the interviews were conducted are in a semi-open way. What was the focalization was the personal experience so they were conducted in a “familiar” environment. This is made to avoid the “in vitro” feeling even if the interviews have been recorded. There is a lot of *talk* about change but I wanted to bring a very *personal* and concrete experience to the matter.

On the first part of the paper what will be discussed is the theoretical part of the paper explaining the main concepts used to understand and to guide the research. Starting from the conception of difference between nature versus man and as a consequence of this dichotomy in the Western world the difference between rural and urban. As a consequence of this strong dichotomy I would like to tackle the question about the “spectacular”. In the Western societies when talking about food it has become something aesthetical rather than something useful. In this part I would like to talk about the loneliness of people created by social media and image. Lastly, the question of seeing things from a new perspective, here explaining the Anthropocene era and changes in domains of rural sociology will be explained. It is about how in the humanities and in academic field there is a re-thinking and de-construction of presuppositions or giving a new fresh perspective on different fields.

In the second part of the paper I would like to discuss and react to the interviews made to the different people. Firstly I would like to interrogate with the responses gotten if these urban vegetable gardens are creating a “3rd space” or “new civil spaces”? And in a second part I would like to take the experience of Marilijn, Tjreed, Frans, Tony, Jos and Thara and react to them. How does the participation in these kind of activity bring to their lives? Does it impact their surrounding? These activists are part of different projects. Nonetheless all three projects stress the same thing. From the beginning of a hobby or passion about gardening, also from the feeling of being lonely they imagined and created their own space.

First Part : Urban versus Rural spaces

Nature and Humans

The fact that food culture is a growing theme for scholars to get interested in demonstrates a will to understand better the environment² as well as questioning presuppositions/customs of everyday life (Like the way to consume and produce food and the diverse implications it has in a specific society and the world). This is mentioned in the book of *the introduction to Food and culture* by Caroline Counihan and Penny Van Esterik.³ “These examples provide some measure of the many texts that have been published in the last decade. Why has this field exploded so? We would like to suggest several reasons for this explosion. ... A second reason is the politization of food and the expansion of social movements linked to food... A third reason is that once food became a legitimate topic of scholarly research , its novelty, richness, and scope provided limitless grist for political, the material and the symbolic...”.Today it is undeniable that since the industrial revolution⁴ the social spaces in Europe have shifted to suit the new lifestyle of consumerism and industry. Indeed Europe has always been considered as an urban space especially because urbanization is connected with civilization, progress and rationality. These ideas that connect the West to rationality, civilization and progress are ideas that are found in literary work about concept such as race or in scholar work on post-colonialism for example.⁵ This is the reason why for example GMO's (Genetically Modified Organism) are connected with this idea of progress. It is by the faculty of men (it's rationality) that they can control and make solutions: by domesticating nature and manipulating it with science. The purpose of the action is

² With the term environment we are referring to what Palsson in refers as environment, it can be from geology to social Palsson Gisli, *Reconceptualizing the “Anthropos” in the Anthropocene : Integrating the social sciences and humanities in global environmental change research*, Environmental science & policy, n28, 2008

³ Counihan Caroline and Van Esterik Penny, *the introduction to Food and culture*, second edition, Routledge 2008 (1997)

⁴ The industrial revolution is used as a marker of change in the modern world by various articles and books when talking about production, consumption and landscape. Like for example in Cosgrove Denis, *Cultural landscapes*, Tim Unwia, ed A European Geography , Prentice Hall (1998), Chapter 5

⁵ For example in the works of Stuart Hall as the Spencer Stephen writes in his book *Race and Ethnicity : Culture, Identity and Representation* ,Routledge, 2014

to mold nature to Human's needs. Europeans connected this idea of progress to science, rationality and manners. In history, the West here talking about Europe(and the North America- but the geographical focus of this paper will deal only with Europe⁶) who led "missions of civilization" to "others". These 'others' were everything that Europe was not might it be countries or their populations.⁷ Jan Nederveen Pieterse says on the concept of "others" is that it depends on the time and space and that the definition can adapt itself. As he says in the beginning of the chapter, "Throughout, designating others and emphasizing their "otherness" have been fundamental to the construction of boundaries of identity and community, between and within societies. Over time otherness has had different meanings, as many as identity. It has referred to cultural differences along the lines of language, religion, civilization, "race", ethnicity, region, nationality, gender, age, and to class, development, ideology, and so forth".⁸ In Europe this "other" is the countryside. It has been the opposite of civilization, progress and urbanity. ⁹Defined only by a way to linger and be calm by the more fortunate who lived there to get out of the city. The city represented stress and work. On the contrary nature brings relaxation. It is a place for vacation and it also has become a place for the wealthy.¹⁰

⁶ What is Europe : Acknowledging the fact that Europe is very vast and there is no intention of homogenizing "Europe? which Europe?" In: Marie-Louise von Plessen (ed.) Idee Europa. Entwürfe zum "Ewigen Frieden". Deutsches Historisches Museum, p17-22 By Wim Blockmans

⁷ Bhabha Homi, *The Location of Culture*, Routledge,(1995),2005

⁸ Pieterse Jan Nederveen, *Europe and its Others*, A Companion to Racial and Ethnic Studies, Blackwell publishing ,Chapter 1, 2002

⁹ Steel Carolyn, *Hungry City : How food shapes our lives*, Vintage Books,2008

Newman J. , Contemporary developments in rural life in Europe, *Sociologia Ruralis*, Volume 6, Issue 3, pages 224–240, (1966) 2008

¹⁰ McLeod Hugh, *The Urban/rural Dichotomy in European and North American Religious History from the Eighteenth Century to the Twentieth*, Social Compass (1998) 2008

http://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/File:Leviathan_by_Thomas_Hobbes.jpg

How did this dichotomy came to be so strong ?

There has always been two ways of seeing man and his relationship with nature and institutions. Let's go back in time and review how philosophers viewed man without institutions (culture or civilization), in the "nature". *By state of nature* what is meant is the view of humans without civilization. Without civilization means without an imposed culture, institutions and customs. On one hand there was the Hobbian way and on the other the Rousseanian way of viewing the *state of nature*. While Hobbes highlighted the nature of man as intrinsically "bad" and his state of nature as chaotic needing rules and institutions to control and regulate As the picture shows there is a king which is ruling the environment. The body of the king is made up of other bodies of the people, nonetheless the head is the one with the crown on it who represents power. In the opposite of this thought we have the Rousseanian thought on nature and institutions. Rousseau believed that it was not the state of nature of man who was bad but the institutions themselves who corrupted man. He argued that pity and compassion something that had been overlooked by Hobbes was also important.

So even in the way of seeing civilization, power and institutions there is a big rivalry and a way of seeing the relationship of nature and man.¹¹

These thoughts helped develop the way we have conceptualized the cities, urbanization versus rurality and nature. The idea that prevailed was the domestication of nature. Man was scared of the untamed and wild because it could lead to chaos as Hobbes predicted. Another thought that was predominant in the beginning of times and that is even more predominant in our contemporary society (Always talking about the West) which is the need for production.¹² As Carolyn Steels puts it about nature and the relation Roman's had with it ,“ The *ager* was distinguished from *saltus*, wild and unproductive nature, which the Romans viewed with disdain, or even dread. To Roman eyes, nature as split into two: the tame and the untamed, the productive and the unproductive, the good and the bad. It was a view that would persist as urbanity strengthened its hold on Western culture (...)”.¹³ So what prevailed was the clear distinction between city and the rural side. The urban was synonym of progress because it was more “institutionalized” (controlled) and rural was less productive because there was less of these institutions (there was a part with less man control) . Although what is evident is that rural and urban spaces are related to one another. As Carolyn Steel states “Nobody in the ancient world ever took their food for granted. The fact that our words “culture” and “cultivate” share the same stem (the Roman *cultus*) tells its own story. Cultivation and civilization in the Graeco-Roman world were inextricably linked.”¹³. Nowadays as the author relates in her book we have lost this notion that we need the rural side to get food in the cities. Citizens do not even questions on their food customs or where the food they eat every day does comes from.

So, there has been a very big change on the view that citizens have on food. (This is in the view of a fortunate average Western person – not including the poor). The institutions that behold the market of food is very different too. There is no traditional market life anymore. Meaning as Steel in her book explains how city life was organized by days of market, and how food production was very visible. Nowadays there are supermarkets. They often have the monopoly on the production of the staple and the final product. This is kept very secret. Like for the provenience, stock and transportation of food.¹⁴ This might be a result of how Bauman considers the contemporary consumer. What he argues is that the contemporary consumer is different from the one in the modern society. He distinguishes between two different epochs. The production epoch (Modernity) and the

¹¹ http://www.academia.edu/3531858/The_State_of_Nature_Thomas_Hobbes_and_Jean_Jacques_Rousseau
<http://www.iep.utm.edu/soc-cont/>

¹² Bauman Zygmunt, *the self in a consumer society*, The Hedgehog review : Identity, Vol 1 n 1,1991 pp.35

¹³ Steel Carolyn , *Hungry city : How food shapes our lives*, Vintage,(2008),2009 pp.17

consumer epoch (nowadays). This is how he defines the contemporary consumer “The consumer of a consumer society, however, is a sharply different creature from the consumer of any society thus far. The difference is one of emphasis and priorities – a shift of emphasis that makes an enormous difference to virtually every aspect of society, culture, and individual life.”¹⁴ What Bauman argues is that the contemporary consumer is always in movement and shifting. Might it be physically but also in his desires. Bauman argues that the contemporary consumer is always in a perpetual appetite. (In an metaphor). He is always hungry for something new but never needs/finds to be satisfied. He also thinks that he has the choice because he has the power to choose among the variety. However, he points out the fact that the consumer can chose amongst a chosen variety. So it is not a real choice. Like for example in Steel’s book when she is talking about the choice of product, “Its success lies in its ability to reduce a highly complex process (food production) to an operation so streamlined that its very product (food) is now subservient to it. As Henry Ford is once supposed to have said, “You can have your Ford any colour you like – as long as it’s black””.¹⁵

If we look at this point on the point of view of the “spectacle “by Chiara Boticci, we can see how the imagination of individuals or even the collective is really limited to the raise of collective imagination and imaginal which is instituted .¹⁶ We can also see GMO’s entering that trend. GMO’s are seeds that have been modified in their core (Their DNA) to fit man’s necessities. (being more rentable (needing less water) for example). Albeit this positive point, there is the creation of a certain variety and it has been shown that when a GMO plant encounters a non-GM plant the GM plant will “kill” the non-GM. GM are also sterile.¹⁸ Two deductions can be drawn from this the first is about the choice – or the erase of this one – and the second is about – the non-respect for nature--.

¹⁴ Bauman Zygmunt, *the self in a consumer society*, The Hedgehog review : Identity, Vol 1 n 1,1991 pp.36

¹⁵ Steel Carolyn , *Hungry city : How food shapes our lives*, Vintage,(2008),2009 pp.59

¹⁶ Boticci Chiara, *The Politics of Imagination*, Birkbeck Law Press,2011,pp.12-13

The Spectacular

<http://www.dailymail.co.uk/femail/article-2509841/Instagram-pictures-food-reduces-enjoyment-real-food-study-shows.html>

If we look at promotional CAP (Common Agricultural policy) videos they stress out the rural side of Europe. This first point as we have seen above is far from reality. Nonetheless it is not on this point that we will dwell on. What is shown in the videos is a very rural side of Europe and how the CAP helps to protect this side of Europe's identity and tradition. What is portrayed and more relevant on these videos are the machines and the final products. There is no highlight on the people who really consume it and produce it. There are "nice" images of what agriculture and rural life is in the European Union.

Nature is something that mass media contributes as a spectacle in the contemporary times. We do not produce from the land we look at it. This can remind the ongoing trend on Instagram (a social media for images)¹⁷ that people post all the time picture of their food and forget to eat it. Looking at social media and the trends that are going on we can discover many of the perception that we have with food. There is a term to call this aesthetical food, it is popularly and

¹⁷ <http://www.dailymail.co.uk/femail/article-2509841/Instagram-pictures-food-reduces-enjoyment-real-food-study-shows.html>

becoming more popular since the 1980's when it was first used in the academics as "food porn". "Food porn" is more a term used by academicians to attract more readers since the trend is to have a wide public so that issues can have a weight.¹⁸ As the author relates, "The very idea of food porn is contentious. Academics presumably like the term because it attracts more readers than less sexy topics (pun intended), while the general public uses the term broadly to describe mouthwatering images in magazines, on TV, or online." What does it mean to associate two things such as something that is usually consumable with something that is not? First of all as the author suggests "Food, when removed from the kitchen, becomes divorced from its nutritive or taste qualities and enters the realm where surface appearance is all-important: "¹⁹as she quotes from critic Richard Magee. The association of porn and food also lead to other ideas such as the fact that it becomes a solely individual experience "At the same time, porn as a cultural artifact gained legitimacy through identity politics (which emphasized personal experience over larger morals and social codes), body and gender theory (which emphasized physical difference as a form of empowerment) and an economic difference ... all the better to be consumed...".²⁰ It also dissociates food from its nutritious value and goes in hand with the sole purpose of watching "Culture is not only about representation but also about doing it. We practice culture, and it takes a lot of practice. This tactile, embodied conception of culture is a useful corrective to culture understood primarily as representation or artifact."²¹ This is what Carlo Petrini refers to in this interview by "Spectacular food".²² He argues that there is all this side of knowing how the food has been produced, questions of identity and tradition that have been lost to leave the place for recipes and shows about food (*Hell's Kitchen* for example). To continue with this idea of spectacle it is because we are in the era of rationality. (as explained above) and imagination (definition of Castoriadis , that it enables the ability that makes us to be able to think "phantasia"- and about the institution of both individual and collective social imaginary (from imagination to imaginary (from subject-oriented to a context-oriented)) that has been instituted by an institution- and definition of Hannah Arendt, to be able to put ourselves in other people's shoes)

¹⁸ McBride Anne e., *Food porn*, *Gastronomica* : The journal of critical food studies, vol 10, no 1, 2014 pp.38

¹⁹ McBride Anne e., *Food porn*, *Gastronomica* : The journal of critical food studies, vol 10, no 1, 2014 pp 38

²⁰ McBride Anne e., *Food porn*, *Gastronomica* : The journal of critical food studies, vol 10, no 1, 2014 pp P42

²¹ McBride Anne e., *Food porn*, *Gastronomica* : The journal of critical food studies, vol 10, no 1, 2014 pp Pp.41

²² <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=khQm5ehq8Pc&list=PLo7NAPjezhYCZrPxPIH5dtaKKvKgZ3DBN&index=25>: Le invasioni barbariche, La7, 2012, Time: 6:37 (Last viewed on 18-06-14)

has been put asides as Chiara Bottici remarks.²³What she argues is that we lack the most relevant information about things. That even if we live in the era of images the status of “truth” has disappeared. To be ‘real’ it needs to reach a large audience, it needs to be “Hollywoodified”. The future is science, rationality, GMO’s and nuclear industries. They are the ones who bring jobs and who use time wisely. Nonetheless this focus on material and the concrete is it lacking or not showing some aspects? Indeed this idea can also relate to the hyperreality of Baudillard. Hypereality is a term to used to exaplin the fact that artifacts that are man made are taken for the reality, making it hard to distinguish between something that is real (what we see in an image) and in what way it is different in the real life.²⁴

Nowadays our “consumerist “society is all about the individual. As we have seen above with the new term of “food porn”. This could be understood as Bauman explains with the continuous want to satisfy our own desires. Not leaving any place to get out of this individual bubble. Social media has been the utensil to fight against this loneliness but is it truly doing so? Or are we being deceived? Looking at videos spread on the internet about social media we could ask ourselves if we are not truly living in a made-up world where even our feelings are becoming artifacts?²⁵ We do not have a touch of reality and of the environment anymore. Maybe it is time to step out of our “individual bubble”? To look at things differently ?

New Perspectives?

Nonetheless, there are changes happening in the West such as movements of “Slow Food” for example. “Slow Food” is a gastronomic/environmental movement which started in Italy by Pietro Petrini and who advocates this lost conscience on food production and

²³ Bottici Chiara, the politics of imagination, Birkbeck Law Press, 2011

²⁴ <http://publish.uwo.ca/~dmann/baudrillard1.htm>

²⁵ <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=4UQLcqYj-b8>

consumption that has been lost by the average European.²⁶ It is a movement that uses other images than the one which has been developed on the rural side. It promotes awareness and conscience on food production mainly. It is a movement that is part of a bigger movement. What is rural life? It is a complex and many sided thing that is also open to both internal and external factors it also an integrating part of social conjecture. As Newman advocates rurality needs to be seen in another point of view than the urban one as he states “Even those areas which still remain physically rural are coming to be regarded as “mentally urbanized “by the rural sociologists. It seems to me that this preoccupation can be explained by the fact that the majority of studies have been conducted in the context of the more developed and therefore urbanized countries of Europe – countries which, by reason of their affluence, are well endowed with agencies, governmental and other, which pose questions for sociological research.”²⁷ The definition that has been predominant is “... what is urban society and what rural? At the Congress in St. Wolfgang in 1962 Kötter (1962a) described urban-industrial society as characterized by respect for the social values of freedom of the personality, adequate income, educational possibilities, upward mobility and participation in cultural institutions. In contrast with this, rural society is commonly assumed to be essentially non-progressive and backwards.”²⁸ Therefore there is a will to de-construct and to challenge what has already been written. The new way of seeing the relationship to nature by man is the *Anthropocene era*. The Anthropocene era (*Anthropo* meaning Human and *cene* meaning new) is a new way to see the interaction between humans and the environment. The environment is all that surrounds human life including nature. It is the building of a bridge between the human production and food. It is about regaining that consciousness of its role of shaping his environment. As Palsson argues the environment was only seen as an object of natural science. “Thus, is illustrated by the dualism of nature and society central to many disciplines.”²⁹ . Nonetheless, today thinking about the matter and including social sciences it accounts also the social-”biosocial and natural-cultural”). Nowadays, because of the global crisis (might be economic and environmental/social) the social sciences see humans as an

²⁶ <http://www.slowfood.com/>

²⁷ Newman J. , *Contemporary developments in rural life in Europe*, Sociologia Ruralis, Volume 6, Issue 3, (1966) 2008, pp.233

²⁸ Newman J. , *Contemporary developments in rural life in Europe*, Sociologia Ruralis, Volume 6, Issue 3,(1966) 2008, pp.233

²⁹ Palsson Gisli, *Reconceptualizing the “Anthropos” in the Anthropocene : Integrating the social sciences and humanities in global environmental change research*, Environmental science & policy, n28, 2013, pp.9

integrating part of the environment. One is not in dichotomy of the other. They are both put in on an equal standard. “Despite the recognition of human activity's growing influence on environmental change, major social science and humanities funding agencies have generally been absent in funding global change research. Nevertheless, virtually all social science and humanities disciplines have at some point taken an interest in human-environment interaction.²³ Continuing with this thematic of change in the outlook of the relationship man/nature and the de-construction or the reviewing of presuppositions. For example in Rousseau’s definition of state of nature he pointed out this same problem of looking at the state of nature from a specific point of view. Rousseau argues that Hobbes viewed the state of nature with the model he already had from his society, elite bourgeois. This is the reason why in Hobbes state of nature man is “bad” and finds the same “evils”. In Dunlap’s article he highlights this specific point that in rural sociology, rurality has always been seen with the eyes of urbanity. New rural sociologists also try to challenge “the mainstream climate science”(For example the IPCC – Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change) or “conservative think tanks” which are the media and politicians.³⁰ This growing trend of the de-construction, from Bhabha’s explanation it is one of the most well-known postmodernist concerns . It is a concern for philosophy, literary criticism, and textual analysis developed by Jacques Derrida. The notion of a "deconstructive" approach implies an analysis that questions the already evident deconstruction of a text in terms of presuppositions, ideological underpinnings, hierarchical values, and frames of reference. A deconstructive approach further depends on the techniques of close reading without reference to cultural, ideological, moral opinions or information derived from an authority over the text such as the author and re-thinking is also about the bigger picture the West.³¹ In Bhabha’s book *the location of culture* he questions the institutions and demonstrates that culture can be found elsewhere than the “institutionalized” or “places made for it”.³² Like when he is talking about the production and fertile place of the museum’s staircase. Where things can encounter and produce things. So that culture can be found elsewhere. This is in contrast with the general idea. For example if we take the definition of culture by T.S Eliot, he does not make any

³⁰ Dunlap Riley E., *Climate change and rural sociology : Broadening the research agenda*, Rural Sociology n75,2010, pp.19

³¹ Bhabha Homi, *The Location of Culture*, Routledge,(1995),2005

³² Bhabha Homi, *The Location of Culture*, Routledge,(1995),2005

difference between culture and civilization (We can ask what civilization he talking about) and he quotes that culture is found in books, newspapers, radio, film and religion. 26All of these things are “institutionalized “they are imagined by an institution like Castoradis pointed out for the imagination.

Second Part : The interviews- Let’s talk *to* the people and not *about* them

New Civil spaces?

(From the Tuin in de Staad)

From the interviews that I conducted there is one point which has been said by all the activists. They all started from a hobby and then they created a community (with the people who were interested in that same hobby or passion). It is about reaching out and creating a “circle”. Not a closed one but a permanent open circle ready to include whomever and to be molded by others. The interviews were conducted in a semi-open method, this was done because each individual is different and all the personal stories are also unique. By using the semi open method of interviewing it gave the respondent more space to bring his singular thought to the discussion as well as creating a more friendlier environment. The interviews range from 20 to 40 minutes. They were conducted in the places where the activists work. On the basis of my literature what I wanted to reveal was: to what extent, these urban vegetable gardens could

mirror or contribute to community building and sustainability in Groningen ? It was only in visiting and talking to the interviewees that other thoughts raised. Such as the fact that these places were unique- not only by their organization and geography- but also by the people who contribute into building them. This made me think of Bhabha's 3rd Space and Bauman's Liquid Modernity. Then what I found was that my initial hypothesis of community and sustainability building as a consequence of being active in such space ,was wrongly asked. It was the fact that they wanted to create a community that opened their consciousness to some environmental questions.

In Bhabha's , *The location of culture*, he argues that there are third spaces that are being created. These spaces for him are illustrated as a stairwell in a museum. The stairwell is a place of encounter and in permanent dynamism. In the introduction of his book, he explains that we are at this point in time in society where it is impossible to look back but that we are neither living in the present because it is always 'escaping us' , as he says "Beginnings and endings may be the sustaining myths of the middle years; but in the fin de siècle, we find ourselves in the moment of transit where space and time cross produce complex figures of difference and identity, past and present, inside and outside, inclusion and exclusion." ³³He also adds the idea of the singularity of the spaces and the reclaiming of a proper identity "These 'in between' spaces provide the terrain for elaborating strategies of selfhood – singular or communal – that initiate new signs of identity, and innovative sites of collaboration, and contestation, in the act of defining the idea of social self." And continuing "It is in the emergence of the interstices – the overlap and displacement of domains of difference – that intersubjective and collective experiences of *nationness*, community interests, or cultural value are negotiated."³⁴ Another point he adds, is that this spaces are "fluid" and not "essential" meaning that they are always in dynamic in construction and that the "elements "that compose this space are heterogeneous and they change all the time. This concept can be reattached to the liquid modernity of Bauman. One of the differences is that Bauman says that we are still living in modernity as opposed to Bhabha that says that we are in the post-modern. Although they both agree on the fact that we are living in a new age where things are in dynamic and in perpetual

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³⁴

progress. When Bauman says that we are still living in the modernity he acknowledges the fact that it is not the same modernity of the past “ As time flows on , “modernity” changes its forms in the manner of the legendary Proteus... What was some time ago dubbed (erroneously) ‘post modernity, and what I’ve chosen to call, more to the point, ‘liquid modernity’, is the growing conviction that change is the only permanence, and uncertainty the only certainty. A hundred years ago ‘to be modern’ meant to chase ‘the final state of perfection’—now it means an infinity of improvement , with no ‘final state’ in sight and none desired.”³⁵

Could this new urban spaces reflect the third space of Bhabha and reflect this idea of liquid modernity of Bauman? Are these people participating in the projects going a step further and still being in this *third space* or *liquid modernity*, instead of “being driven” reacting and taking back the space? Are they aware of the space?

<http://v1tal.com/tag/editorial/>

*On top a parody of the popular and famous Leonardo da Vinci's Vitruvian man. Representing that man (obese) is taking much more space breaking the circle – because as man gets bigger and takes more space the environment (the planet and all its resources) is not expanding. Leonardo da Vinci drew this to show that all in the world is measured by man – this is an addition contributing to the same reasoning of the Anthropocene era that believes that we should acknowledge the impact of man in his environment.

³⁵ Bauman Zygmunt, *Liquid Modernity*, Polity Press (2000),2012, Foreword to the 2012 edition : Liquid modernity revisited pp.9

(Google maps)

From the individual to back to the community

These urban vegetable gardens (All the different projects – The farm, (Merljin and Tjeerd) the social vegetable garden(Tuin in de stad) and the solidarity project (Toenje)) might be all be different yet their type of location is the same. They are in the periphery but not so much. They are a little outside of the urban area of Groningen but they still touch the rural side

also. Nonetheless, they are relatively near the urban- city. They are in the *interstices*, in the middle. This allows to have a contact with both part of the city. It also allows a kaleidoscopic range of people to visit and participate to the activities. In this aspect of their location and the people who participate in the activities we might say that they could be like the Third Space of Bhabha? Additionally these spaces are always in permanent construction since all the people who participate bring “something new”. This can also relate to the liquid modernity of Bauman? Since they never know exactly how the project will develop because even if they have an aim they do not know whether or not they will manage to achieve it.

This projects are also part of creating a new civil space? This idea is explained in Alison Leitch’s *Slow Food and the Politics of Pork Fat : Italian Food and European Identity*. Indeed, these different alternative urban vegetable gardens contribute in creating new spaces with new public memories. As Leitch puts it in talking about the Slow Food movement as part of new civil spaces ,“Coinciding with these trends has been the rapid emergence of an influential independent non-profit sector of the economy and the development of new civil spaces fostering alternate forms of civic associationism.”³⁶. These associations are part of the branch of civilians taking back their space. Wanting to be “particular “in the sense of identity (against homogenization). As Leitch argues about the tendency of Europe to homogenize like for example with the EURO or with GMO’s with the monoculture, these new social spaces create and celebrate their own and others identities. Defining themselves and taking control of their own destinies.

From the community to the environment

It is about making that liaison between body and mind. It is reattaching these two things by the “meat”. The meat here in the situation of the urban vegetable gardens is the activists. Like seeing it in a perspective of the Anthropocene that the man is on the same level as his environment. Man is included and takes part of his environment. It is a change of perspective moving away

³⁶ Leitch Alison, *Slow Food and the Politics of Pork fat : Italian Food and European Identity*, Counihan Caroline and Van Esterik Penny, *The introduction to Food and culture*, second edition, Routledge 2008 (1997) pp. 384

from the dichotomy (of men versus nature). Realizing that things complete each other and one cannot live without the other. The earth needs us (humans) and we need the earth for our survival. It is by engaging themselves and taking care of the community that the activists became aware of the surroundings. The focus of the activists was more about the community and then as an effect it was about taking care of the environment. So it is about seeing life as part of something and reaching out to people (Getting out of the “individual bubble”) that people can start to acknowledge the surroundings.

This is illustrated in all the interviews made. All of the participants where glad to get to meet other people and be connected to other people to build a project. The effect that this connection procured was a consciousnessnes of the environment.

Marlijn and her husband where well aware of all the hardship it takes to be able to get even a simple tomatoe. What they firstly discuss about

Conclusion:

From the passage to an ancient, modern and contemporary consumer society, the relation of nature and man has evolved. His relation to food production and consumption reveal these

links like a mirror. From the passage of a production society to a consumer society the place or urban and rurality have also evolved. There has always been a view of man as superior to nature. Nature has been seen as unproductive and wild if not tamed and controlled by man. This has been the dominant view by man in society. Only the minority had a view of man and nature on a horizontal instead of a vertical view. Nowadays, we are slowly going back to this idea of respecting and living in harmony with nature. GMO's have wanted to impose themselves as the science rooted rational choice. Nonetheless, it is undeniable that all over the world they are facing a lot of contestation. The crisis (not only economical but also social) has come. It is challenging the way we produce, consume and view our (food) in the environment. It is by asking ourselves questions about the things in our daily lives and trying to view them with an open mind that we might find the answers for the crisis. Getting interested about the people and not only talking about them is what truly enables solutions to be found. We can view these new spaces between rural and urbanity as new spaces for expression. The change might come from the interstices. It is by getting out of our "individual bubble" and from the "spectacular" that real feelings, emotions and imagining solutions for a better tomorrow can take place.

NOTE:

This paper acknowledges that definitions of urban and rural are particular to each geographical space. In any case it is intended that there is a homogenization of the situation in a universal scale. It also acknowledges the fact that the researcher (me) has a subjective point of view. This is shown by the choosing of the material and the way to tackle the theme of urban/rural.

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Le invasioni barbariche, La7, episode 9, 2012

ANNEX:

- Frans on the right and Tony on the left in the Tuin de stad.

(<http://www.detuinindestad.nl/>)

Time of the interview : 22:02 minutes

Date of the interview:21/06/2014

Interview to Tony Lorder (She comes to help 3 to 4 a week and she is a permanent member)

Flavia Curatolo: Hello I would like you to first present yourself , what is your name your occupation and if you could tell me a little bit about this project?

Tony Lorder: I am Tony Lorder. I am 57 years old. My original occupation is teacher in languages (Dutch language). Later on I worked in education for parents. I don't know the real English name To teach parents how to raise their children. If they have trouble raising their children. Right now I'm not working anymore – not for money anyways. Now I am working here. Since 4 years. You want me to tell you something about the project?

F.C :Yes, please.

T.L: Tuin in de stad , is where I am working 2 times or 4 times a week. It is a place not in the center of the town but still in the town. It is a green spot where everybody is welcomed you can come here to have a cup of tea or coffee. Walk a little bit to see what is growing here. We sell plants and we try to do everything as natural as possible.

F.C Why is it important?

T.L : Because we do not want the flowers and vegetables to be poisoned by all kind of stuff to do to make them grow bigger, faster and more beautiful.

F.C: Like GM-GMO's ?

T.L: Yes, so we try to do it as natural as possible so we don't use any artificial stuff here for the plants. Just the water and biological soil. What we do here is not easy to say, because everyone all people who come here have a different goal to be here, different reason,. I came here because I like to get my hands dirty from the soil, you know?

F. C: How do you feel when you do that ?

T. L: forget everything, time other people, I don't think much at that moment. I just do my thing.

F.C: But how did you start this? How did you know that you wanted to do this?

T. L :4-5 years ago I was ill . I had a burn out , is that the a term?

F. C: Like depression?

T. L: No, like too tired to do anything from work now I always worked and worked and I had a lot of stress, and then my body and mind aid no more. And I was really...depressed also at the moment. I was so tired I couldn't work anymore so I just stayed home for a year. Then I came here with a friend. Who said come, see this! Maybe you like this so then I came here and I stayed 2-3 times a week. And from that day forwards I felt that I had to be outside always being in the open air not being between four walls . if I'm here I'm free I really feel free.

F.C: What about the friend who told you to come here ? How did she knew about the project? Was she your neighbor ?

T.L : No she's a friends but she is also coordinator from the volunteering work to get volunteers for all kind of works in the city. She knew this place because sometimes people come here, because she says to people to go there and see if you like it if you want to do something voluntarily. So she knew it from her work then she thought maybe its good for you so she took me.

F.C : Did you stay here only because you feel good in nature or also because you found some friends? How do you think about the people who are around here ? How are they?

T.L: It's different people, young people, older people, you know it's just a how do you say? You can be here what you are. You don't have to be more than you really are. I am me. And that's me. And Frans is Frans and that's enough. Everybody can be him or herself here, you don't have to be who look beautiful. You just are welcomed here. And that's nice here, because there are some people who are stranger and the other one who is a little bit... fast... and that's ok. I think it's too much for me now I can go to work. I can do what I want here. Everybody can do what they want if it fits in the concept.

F.C: Who do you plant vegetables? Who gets to eat them?

T.L : We do. The people who work here. Up to now.

F.C: Do you also shop at Albert Heijn? Or supermarkets?

T. L : Yes I do , I don't always buy biological vegetables sometimes I think it's too expensive. So I buy normal vegetables. The most vegetables I buy in the supermarket are from the market : street market.

F.C :Do you think that this project is contributing to what?

T.L : Its contributing to the cohesion to the area around here. A lot pof people knows us from the other side of the road. People learn to know each other and have a good time sometimes people who met here are going away and. Do also things to do with each other. I think it's also important to have a place like this where children can come and play with their parents and the

parents meet each other they talk to each other. New contacts. I think its important in every part of the town there should be a place like this.

F.C But wouldn't be better if it was in the rural space because there would be more space and more green? Is it important that it is not in the town but close to it ?

T.L: I think it's important to have it in the town because it makes us part of the normal life of people. Not everyone has a car who can go easily outside. People have a bike and everyone can come here. So if it's outside of course there is more space but you can go there if you like. So walking in the woods, that's ok but I think that is important that people can come walking or by bicycle you know it's easy to get here.

F.C: How did you learn how to plant and di you learn everything?

T.L: By looking, asking by reading something and sometimes you do it wrong so it fails so you do it again. It's just from looking how other people do it and ask, and I don't know everything but that is ok.

F.C: How do you think the biggest achievement of this project was? Or is going to be?

T.L: Achievement is what we have accomplished?

F.C :Yes.

T.L: We are not ready yet it is developing, but I think that meeting place. Just a place where you can come and that's a big achievement. In summer you know , because in winter we always were clothes because it's too cold but now we are going to renovate so we hope that this winter we will be open so we can do activities for people or people can do activities and we can talk about it and if it's possible its possible. We also want to grow plants now inside in winter because it's warm then. So we can grow our own biological flowers an you know? So we can sell them . Because flowers is very difficult to buy not biological. You have to do it yourself it seems during winter. Because the flowers we always sold was one year flowers they were not biological but we don't know where we need to buy them so we will have to do it ourselves because we don't want to sell these plants anymore. We want to do natural

F.C: How do these projects contribute to the future?

T.L :What we are trying to achieve for the future is that people will come here and work here and are going to feel that this place from them. And they can do something here. For example there is someone who wants to make a pottery, putting the plants in them. And he wants to do it here and someone wants to sell it here. That is ok is someone wants to do it here. That is possible. But that is his responsibility then. That part. People can do their thing here but they are also responsible for it. Sometimes it's still so that we, have to feel, responsible for everything, but that not possible that's too much.

F.C: The way it works here is that you have responsibility but it is an open space for other ideas.

T.L: Yes

T.L: It's kind of how do you call it?... Like an corporation, everyone does part and together you are one.

F.C: How do you think this globally?

T.L: I think that the meaning of doing things more natural and that thinking about how you live and how you eat and how you treat animals for example I think that in the western world for now people are being more aware of it. Thinking about the environment and you know? China is also a very big country and I don't think they think so much about the environment but I maybe it's coming. I think it's a western idea from thinking about how you live and thinking responsible for the earth.

F.C: One last question: Do you think that this project contributes to public memory ?

T.L: What's public memory?

F.C: Going back to tradition? Like for example your daughter is she going to be implicated?

T.L: Like taking it with her? I think that when my parents were young they lived with each other in a town family lived there and these people move everywhere, from some part people are looking for something like this. Recognition some kind of that you are a part of something. Meeting other people. In the old days it was normal to speak to someone in the street . But now people are working and going away. I think that what's people always do, some people close related to, that's so yeah, I think but that's not sometimes started here but what people always will do. Find a way to develop and see other people. And of course some people are very lonely in this times. And these people always come here. If you are alone if you come with 2 or 3 it's ok. I don't know if my daughter will give you the same answer? But I think that it's not new people always search for.

F.C : Would you like to add something?

T.L: No.

Time of the interview : 24:19 minutes

Date of the interview:21/06/2014

Interview to Frans Kerver (He is responsible to have founded the Tuin in de stad)

Flavia Curatolo : Hello, could you please present yourself your name and your occupation and why did you start this project? And tell me about the project?

Frans Kerver: My name is Frans Kerver. With my partner I took the initiative for this project. At the beginning it was not a project at all it was just a place. We both work very much time in front of the computer so we had a feeling that we wanted to work some hours a week outside. And we got to this place who was a greenhouse for a long time but there was no one busy here. So we called the city hall and we asked if we could start here and it was alright if the neighbors don't complain we could do everything. so we started here just being here in the garden and then other people came for coincidence, they were curious, what are you doing? Can I help? So spontaneously there was a kind of a group inner circle and the larger group in the outer circle. And some people just coming and helping for just when they like it, it is a very fluid group. It's not an organizational or institution group and that's good. And we try to rebuild this place for a spot nature city, natural environment. We don't design we just take a look and have little plants and just change something. It's important that things we do and how it looks it is like organic growing. Not designing it on paper and then building it and just doing the right thing together what you think you have to do.

F.C When did this project start?

F.K :It started in 2009 and after 3 years we made it bigger and we took part in a competition where we got a lot of money and we could rebuild the place because in winter time we cannot do nothing because it's too cold. So we are now with neighbors and friends and anyone who likes it rebuilding the place so we can do activities in the winter also. The most important thing is that it is a place where people are welcome and just meet each other and make plans to do stuff together

F.C: Who comes here?

F Its nice here because most of the time these kind of places are for the hip lefties, hipsters, but this spot is in an environment where very much normal people not hip people., so the nice thing here it's a good mix from otherwise young hipsters but *also pensoniates*-older people and little children and their mothers. One half come from the neighborhood and the surroundings and the rest comes from the rest of the city and further on.

F.C: What relationship do you have with these peoples?

F.K: What do you mean?

F.C: How do you feel about the people who come here? How is the dynamic? Are there any permanent people?

F.K: It's very fluid we don't try to build an organization we try to connect with everyone the reason why people come here can be very different and what they do here is very different. For example there are people just buying plants and do nothing else. But there are also people from the direct neighborhood, for example when we have plant exchange and seed exchange and

things like a market there is more people from the neighborhood that come here because they like it and they can meet each other. But when we have lectures there are people that care about something about nature or environment most of the time there is people who are interested about the subject. There is a big network in town for city agriculture/city farming . We meet each other. Like I can go there they come here and we exchange stuff like seeds and plants and ideas, craftwork... Also there is a kindergarten that come with the children to play here also mothers and fathers they come for the rabbits and the chickens or the trampoline.

F.C: Because this place is not really in the outskirts of the city, would it be easier due to the place? Does the location play a role?

F.K : For me it's very important because it's like a hidden green spot between the houses and the flats and I think it's very important for people that there is such places in the middle of the town so they can come here you don't have to travel to go there it's here it's just around the corner.

F.C: How does it connect with the city? Do you think it's kind of like a little paradise?

F. K: It's not a paradise that's a big promise. It's not a paradise. When you connect to people you get a relation and you will be friendly but no relation goes without fight so it's very important when you take someone serious that you are on the same level. When things happen you also have to talk about things. So when we are building we are very much yelling with each other on how to fix things. I think it has a good purpose because when in the western world money creates the illusion that you don't need anybody else because you can buy surfaces etc.. it is an illusion that you are independent and when everybody is very individual feeling independent there is missing something because we are not living together just living near to each other. What is important here is that we learn to live with each other.

F.C: How are you involved in this project personally?

F.K: With all my heart. We spend a lot of time here and a lot of hours but it doesn't feel like work. When I work at home .I am a copywriter, if it was the only thing it would be very lonely. So here I like no day is not the same . Every hour something else can happen. So I'm not in control and this is what I like.

F.C: Is it your passion?

F.K: Yes.. I'm a bit paradox I am a very social person it's my family history I am the youngest from a big family. In my family there was always a lot of things going on.. noise, people, friends etc.. and when I got out of the house and when I got adult and wife and children etc.. I will always feeling lonely and a little busy... that they are not interested.. What I find here is the vivid life and when I shut the door here and I 'm going home and I live in the country side and I have all the freedom.

F.C: Are the children also involved in this project?

F.K :No, my oldest girl she hates it here. She thinks its rubbish and muddy and not a nice good place and where nothing is fixed. In her heart maybe she is proud that we are doing it but it's not her thing. My son.. my youngest daughter she come here she likes it here, she likes this thing.

F.C: How do you see this project in the future?

F.K :Oh gee... when we started we had no plan no design and the goal was Now. That is also good because the whole world is planning and what did it get us ? I think it's very important to live now living in nature and making stuff and things that are really concrete it is good enough .I hope that more people get involved and we can make a profitable place for growing plants seeds. People can work here and get a living: a *hurika* thing and a terrace of the water. I like to find and mix people who have luck in life and people who have bad luck. So they mix together and the people who have good luck and the people who have either good luck and bad luck meet.

F.C : You plant vegetables here right?

F.K: Now we have Ria who has the background. And we want to grow from seeds 100% biological I don't know if it will work.

F.C: How do you eat?

F.K : We both have jobs and that's how we make a living we work as much as we can.

F.C: So you go to the supermarket?

F.K: Yes but it's because the ground is spoiled everything we, it's not for eating, it's not a place to farm on a large scale because the ground is not good.

F.C: You need to wait for the soil to get better?

F.K: The main thing is not the farming, in the other side, there are some citizens who have a square the farming here is not the main thing. The plants we sell must of the plants are not for eating just for being a plant.

F.C: How did you learn how to plant ?

F.K: I know very little and from people who come here knowledge is very easy to get connect with people. When don't know something you can easily

F.C: Do you pass it on to people?

F. K: There is a Facebook and there is some website but it's not structural or formal, its more by influencing physically. Groningen is very small I know a lot of city farmers.

F.C: Is it like a way of networking?

F. K:yes

F.C: What is the biggest achievement has been and how do you see it in the future?

F.K: I do not know... I'm very proud that we are still going on because it's not easy because you have to fight against rules and regulations. And it is good that we are still in speaking terms with the city hall, I hope that we can stay here and get a nice place not a .. I hope we can get a corporation where people can get a living not rich living but a good living,. But the longer that I am here that lives have successful moments and failure. It's nice to not have to worry so much. You do not have to be depressed by failure. More and more I realize in some way all people are connected, the awareness of being together. It is not a very material, not material things I am proud of. The experiences for me and for other people.

F.C: With GM you could do it faster controlled and organized?

F.K: First thing we have to build a more functional base with good water and good toilets and heating/ And there is supposed to come a local shop. And we are thinking to have a local brand like made in Groningen. And it gets known by other people. And it's not like we have a land and tomorrow it happens. We have to work to get food so it's our spare time. Fits not something linear

F.C :Do you think that this project could contribute to a public memory?

F.K :It's because its growing everywhere we are part of a movement everything is changing on many aspects so it's kind of in the air.

F.C: you think it's part of a global movement?

F.K: Yes because it happening everywhere, that's the strange thing it's like its in the air.. yeah

F.C I am done with my questions, do you want to share something else?

F.K: The important of the research that you have bringing stories and make a structure and you see more these spots and it helps to gets better we are part of the same

- Left Tjeerd and right Merljin

(<http://stadsakker-kwekerij.blogspot.nl/>)

Time : 47:24 minutes

Date: 20/06/14

Interview to Marlijn Albering (She cultivates- she is the farmer) and Tjeerd Andriga (He is her partner and he helps her but it is not his main job)

Flavia Curatolo :So I am going to start the interview and I would like you to present yourselves, and tell me your name and occupation and why did you start this project and and tell me a little bit about the project?

Merlijn Albering :So I guess I will begin and then Tjeerd will complete.

M.A :I used to be a facility manager and I made nice surroundings for a good facility to stay for elderly people. A couple of years ago I decided to make a living from my hobby and I wanted to try to make a living out of : from growing your own vegetables. I think its better because its better to be independent from the big companies. Like the supermarkets we know.

Tjeerd Andriga :Where we have gotten the wine.

M.A: Yes where we have gotten the wine. That is why 4 years ago I talked to the government and I made a presentation about my plans. And I fit exactly in the food policies of the government of the city here. So they were very enthusiastic . They wanted to support me and to find me a piece of land and I wanted to be very close to the city so you can have not so many km between the farmer and the customer, but it takes years and years to find a good piece of land. So we started a shop to support everything in the city to build their own vegetables. In the balcony or terraces. We started that 2 years ago and it was a very good success. We have to grow because we can't live from it but we are growing.. One year ago the government found this piece of land after 5 or other pieces... And I took a look and I was sold. I was impressed by the piece of land. Because there you have your customers in the other side you have the agricultural land the farm land and then you have the industrial area for the Netherland and abroad for sugar. That is the big agro business there. And it took us a year to get all the permits to be sure that the ground was not polluted and we were allowed to start the 1st of January. And in the last 4-3 and half months we did everything that is around you .Since half way February. We started with the bricks. And it was a little difficult because at first you needed the bricks otherwise we couldn't place the containers and if we did not have the containers we couldn't bring the tractor and we could have not prepared the soil, so it was a huge project but it was going very well.

T.A :Although we had a lot of rain in the beginning but everything worked out in the end...

M.A : And we painted by ourselves or by help of our family and *provincy* also gave us agriculture stimulation-grants.

F.C: And besides the family and the government is there anybody else who helped you start this project ? Financially and physically ?

M.A : Not starting. Now we have some help but we started by ourselves. We are an entrepreneur family. It's not the first enterprise we started.

F.C Could I ask you to present yourself?

T.A : My name is Tjeerd Andriga and I'm an associate professor in artificial intelligence and from September I will be officially a 100 % working for the University College but basically I'm 100% member of the University College. I had a good day today ! I had a time when I did my PHD and Merljin had to suffer some sacrifices and I told her that when she would find her passion I would also do my sacrifices. I am still waiting to making these sacrifices actually.

M.A : I think you think this is a good passion.

T.A : Yeah I think it's a good passion and it's great fun to participate in this .

M.A :Because it is changing your whole life.

T.A :Yes it is changing my whole life. Yes basically yes...not my whole life ... but we are live now here instead of a very nice home

M.A: With a toilet, shower and water .

T..A: But, content wise, I don't mind doing some of the work here

M.A : You have to do something tonight so..

T..A: I have to something tonight probably that

M..A: No cover everything again

T.A: I have a special interests in geo politics. And especially geo politics and cognition. And of course agriculture is very important for geo politics, GMO's , agribusiness, the fact that we used to have one world with all kind of farms and now basically the only way you can have a farm is grow bigger and therefore making sure that the small farms are destroyed basically so that leads to a situation where all the farms are part of the big globalized agriculture . That is extremely uniform, extremely fragile and sensitive to everything what I want to do is help to bring resilience back to everywhere basically and also here. So this is my concrete...

M.A :You try from the top and I do it from the bottom.

T.A: Merlijn ...

M..A : I do the work...and he is doing the talking!

T.A : I have the philosophy and the vision!

M.A: I also have the vision!

T.A: I have the theory...

M.A: I can present my vision in 3 minutes and you can't..

F.C : Can I ask you what's your relationship? Or is it too personal?

M.A : We met 21 years ago. We are like married, but we are not.

T.A : Every year we have to decide if we want to stay together, and we do. We met sea kayaking

F.C : You met by a passion ?And today your passion has grown into this?

M.A: Yes, no time for sea kayaking anymore.

F.C: Coming back to what you said about the resilience and the fact that today you are acknowledging the fact that your farm in the middle of the customers and industrial area, how do you see this place? Because you do not want to be isolated but at the same time you want to be close to the city so how do you see this space? How does it connect to both worlds?

M.A : Well you will see the difference if you meet Frans from Tuin in de stad. This place is a company. We work hard every day to be a little bit productive. It is not a place everyone is allowed to visit, because you have to work and if everyone does the visiting and does the chit chat you cannot combine that with working efficiently. If you see Frans that's the place to meet. More the social. And that's how the city farming started, with the social part.

T.A : Re-started actually. It used to be very normal .In the city farming everybody would be growing their own vegetables. Everybody would be growing some small things to make the typical staple foods. Outside of the town so the wheat and things like that, that was grown fairly far from the town but if you look at the map of Groningen like the 1700 it is all gardens . It is incredible. Every house had a garden

F.C :In the old times?

M.A : In the 1700 around that time.

T.A : So for me if you ask me how I see this space I see it as the future.

M.A: Back to the future.

T.A : Well we will have more older people in the future we will have probably the globalized economy running into all kind of big problems. It is actually already running into big problems... t's actually extremely fragile. Like with the crisis or terrorist attacks or whatever.. The local people have to do their work again and be resilient again, become resilient again, and then we need examples .I hope that... we are amongst the first among the Netherlands to show that that this is very feasible and that it is a very good way of leaving. And that the rest of the neighbors will follow?

F.C :How do you feel about it yourselves? How do you see this project?

M.A :Lifework. I am not going to die here but...

A.T : One of the things that are really real. You are not working for some kind of company in which you have to push papers and things that are meaningless... and even if you help people, you help them because their problems probably were created by other people so they can deal with more problems. This is food, high quality living.

M.A : And you do it for someone. It's nice to have a vegetable garden for your family but it is even more special to do it for customers. Really enjoy that you are growing vegetables for them, because they don't have space or they do not like to do it... lack of time and that is special...

F.C: So you are not only doing it for personal reasons? You are not only following a passion, you are doing it for a community.

M.A : Actually it is part of the passion. Well I did it at home and gave the vegetables away because I produced too much. It was always fine, the neighbors were always delighted to have fresh vegetables. And now we have 50 customers who paid in advance for their vegetables and they believe in our farm and I am happy with them. The farmer and the customer are closely related. If my customers say that they want other carrots or potatoes or just pumpkins I can change my planning and give them the food they want.

F.C : So do you feel like there is an exchange between the customers and the producer? Is it not like in supermarkets- they take what there is?

M.A :Well in supermarkets the customers have to buy what there is... but here you know that it is produced with heart and care...

T.A : With the consideration with pretty much everything...

M.A : With the consideration of the customer...I cannot do this without the customer and I don't have a marketing plan to push my vegetable to the markets.

F.C : What about the environment do you plant certain thing in certain times? Or, you have to satisfy the customer... but the soil can give what it can give...

M.A : Well that is the function of the customer. Nowadays, the customers ask for strawberries around Christmas. If my customers ask me this I will explain that I can't grow strawberries around Christmas. I can have other nice stuff but no strawberries. Nowadays the customer ask and the farmer has to grow that stuff.

T.A : So basically the what the customer is doing is growing fossil fuels into strawberries. Because in summer you don't need energy . But in winter you need more energy..

M. A: And then you try to explain to the customers, and they really understand this.

F.C : So you think there is a lack of communication or information? To be closer to the customer? That if you see the product just in the supermarket you will not ask yourself so many questions?

M.A : Yeah! And even when the customers grow their own tomatoes they understand the time it costs to grow a tomatoes and then you understand why one kilo of tomatoes costs more than one euro. Because if you grow them by yourself you know I have them water every day afor 3 months and then I have 6 tomatoes. Then you like more what you get you and you appreciate it more and you want to pay more for a good tomatoes. A good price for the farmer.

F.C :How did you learn how to garden? Like how you should plant? What kind of things you should plant? How to take care of them?

M.A : First I just started. We moved into a plot in Friesland and the next day I started a vegetable garden, just out of the blue . I did it for 12 years. 4 years ago when I decided to start a real farm I thought well it takes time before we get a plot so I will follow the organic dynamic schooling. We have a school in *Dronte* in the Netherlands where they teach organic dynamic farming. During those two years I worked in another vegetable farm to learn the skills.

T.A : You learn the theory, and that place is the place to be to learn.

M.A : Actually my trainees are going to study there. You learn how to work when you are working with someone .

F.C : So it is basically memory that it is passed on? Because they are seeing you and then they do it?

M.A/ T.A : yes.

M.A : The nicest thing for example is that we were harvesting the cauliflower and I worked at the farm and the farmer said this one is ready and this one is not. I was looking and I could not see the difference. After 3 or 4 weeks: That cauliflower is ready and that one is not ready! You cannot explain when it's ready. Its nature so you have to learn to see. It is not science.

T.A: It is definitely not an easy decision process. It takes experience, doing and playing... its not something that it only a mental activity.

M.A : I cannot say that I will put the lettuce and in 6 weeks I can say it. Now it's too warm and too dry later on it will be too cold.. and it can be one week earlier or 2 weeks later ... Or we get some bugs or other .. we had some terrible rain last week... and the lettuce was swimming there... You cannot make a protocol.

F.C :How do you organize and predict?

M.A : Well I make a planning a very good planning but the result is always different. You never know what and when but the order is more or less the same. You start with the seed and you end up with a plant. The time range every year is different. And this year we have to learn about the soil and this takes 2 to 3 years to know how it reacts to water, heat, beasts...

F.C : Do you feel part of the community? Besides the relationship farmer/customer? What kind of relationship do you have between the neighbors and the industrial world?

M.A : Well we already met a lot of neighbors. We have not met the people from the factories yet... I called them half a year ago or something , and I said to myself: nice we are going to get neighbors. They are making sugar they have sugar beets and they make the sugar. Later on we are going to farm and make pies as well on the farm. So I need sugar. Is it able to get some sugar? Because it is a 100 meters away it is very close by. They said : No you can go to the Albert Heijn or a very large wholesaler. They were not able to sell it directly. They couldn't explain why. Too difficult or it is not for customers.

T.A : In the shop Merlijn has a local products. Can we do something with that? If you want to buy tons then we are talking or else we are not interested. They are not interested in the neighborhood. They are only interested in the sugar price. They are leaving if they cannot have more money. And they don't understand the customers.

M.A :It is everyone who is biking to the farm and mostly daily and they get a chat not more than 10 minutes . they are interested in what you're doing they are my customers and I am their farmers. Corporations ...the people who are consuming this are people not the corporations?

T. A :Nice marketing things. Then if you look at this it's all wheat not necessarily GMO, although many things are..

F.C: What is your opinion concerning GMO's?

T.A :You lose your choice and you are completely at the mercy of what they are producing.

M.A: Soybeans you don't have to be there so you get a small amount of insects so the insects who are there . They do not have a backup. When the tomatoes don't sell well I have cucumbers. That makes you flexible and independent.

T.A : Resilience again...

MA : That makes you flexible and independent.

F.C : Adaptable well to the environment and taking care of the environment and what people need as you explained before you can't plant something and if no one wants it what are you going to do with it?

MM/TA : Yeah...

F.C And what do you think this will benefit future generations?

MA: I think it will but I am very positive.

T.A: I'm also very positive I think we were led by a lot of propaganda into a way that we do not want to go and we are gradually discovering that we are in a place that makes no sense actually if you think about it . We have the big agribusiness that never proved that it could be sustainable. It only proved that it could be successful if it grew every year. It was kind of that it can only be existed in one situation growth. Growth will always be met by physical limitations.

F.C : Your nice was inspired somewhere. She did not get the idea out of the blue, also in your family is the future generation? Even if you can have an impact to the future generation?

M.A : I believe I am the bottom up if you see the top down approach. I believe if I create a good world around me for my surroundings, for my people and for my customers then I make a small paradise. If everyone does that we makes small paradises then it will grow together.

F.C : and you think it can go from Groningen, from locally to a Global thing?

T.A: I think it can we are the first in Groningen but we are thousands or 10 thousands in the world

F.C: For example the conference you were talking to me about there were people all over the Netherlands ?

M.A / T.A :Yes

T.A But they were not starting they were talking

M.: But a quarter I guess where doing something with vegetables and 10% was trying to make a living on it, because that is always a discussion with the *Wageningen* The University of agriculture, the university of agriculture in the Netherlands You cannot make a living with city farming point. But you are I'm proving it. It takes a couple of years but you get the same income as a farmer because the farmer next door has to pay the loans, the machines for the seeds. I have a lower income and lower coasts. This guy who will visit me will wants to know if it's possible to make a living with it. But then you get a discussion about how much do you make in an hour? No I don't earn so much in an hour but I have a good place to stay and I make people happy and I can buy a bottle of wine and my bread form the supermarket so I do not need more money and bigger income.

T.A: And if you want to do something nice you can just go in the garden

M.A: I don't need to go somewhere nice like to parties to get rid of my energy

F.C: You both are the only ones to take care of all the spaces?

M.A: I have two students who help me and I have one volunteer and I have the family and my

T.A: Make me feel guilty...

F.C :Do you think that your garden will be passed onto the niece?

M.A: She is very impressed with what I do . Now she is in a phase she's 16 and boys are more fun. Maybe in 15 or 20 years wouldn't be surprised

F.C: Can you give me some numbers? Like how big is the farms and the vegetables you use? You told me that you were going to plant some fruits in the future ?

M.A: We have 2 hectares we started with 2 thousand square meters and we will grow in 4 or 5 years to fill up the whole piece of land. We will have 50 hundred square meter fruits we will start next year.

T.A: Actually this autumn. So we have to plant all the fruit.

M.A: We started the 1st of January 2014 and we have a polytunnel from 200 square meters. But we will expand to 600 hundred in the next years if we have the finance. Our investment is 45 thousand and that includes a good place to stay when it's raining. We try to grow 40 kind of vegetables but that will grow slowly like rhubarb, that will harvest next year. We do it all organic. Local is the new organic.

T.A: If you want to use the manure for horses it's very difficult to get biological manure we will ask a farmer to give us the manure and it will be local.

M.A: we try to get all the suppliers this one is coming from, we try to do it all close by, when I give the local community the money they come by the farm .

T.A: I have a new idea yoyo ideas, the 3rd of July the UCG will have their opening day but the food will be provide and all the vegetables will come from you it will be for 50 people.

- Left Jos and right Ruth

<http://www.toentje.nl/>

Time : 27:41 minutes

Date: 23/06/14

Interview to Jos Meijers (he was the initial person responsible for the Toentje) and Ruth (Is a voluntary that comes to help when she has time)

Flavia Curatolo: Hello I would like you to first present yourself , what is your name your occupation and if you could tell me a little bit about this project?

Jos Meijers : I took the initiative to start this project. I worked with the food bank. I worked a lot with people for the food supply.

Ruth: Free Food resource/food sharing

J. M: People who do not have money and food at all and I wanted to make a change in the city. I was lucky because here in Groningen they had some money for the project (And the food bank) This is the way we have gotten started. It took 1 year and a half to talk with the neighbors, the government, and all kinds of people to arrange all this. And in march we started. We were lucky to have 20-30 volunteers who helped us a lot. we are going to produce food. That is the first main goal. Second goal is to earn some money as well because . We are going to do a lot of activities. We are going to start a shop across the street. And sell vegetables and herbs. Like DYS – craftsman ships Like candle making foods we have a lot of designers working there that can present their work.

F.C: Who help you financially?

J.M :The government and we have a lot of sponsors for the soil and the food berries. The Rabo bank who gave us money for the green house. So we had a lot of sponsoring as well. So we had a lot of help in the beginning from sponsoring. And now we are self-reliant so we can arrange other ways to finance our project.

F.C: What about the physical help? Work the field and the other activities?

J.M: There is a whole bunch of different people. You see a lot of different people here. People who still study . People who have jobs and wanted to do something besides that. People in between jobs like Ruth .And the age varies as well from their 20 to 60

F.C :What kind of relationship do you have with everyone?

J.M :A very open one. We have an open communication with everybody. So if there is a problem or somebody has some criticism we have an open communication so we respect everybody. No matter who or she is. Or where she is at in her/his life. People have different times so it's ok if they only have one morning to help us. We really have a nice understanding. All the people who work here took the initiative to come and work here. So we are not like a project who says to all the people who are in between jobs or who rely on social support you must work here.

F.C: Of what I have understood you produce and you redistribute the foods to less fortunate people.

J.M: Via the Foods bank, that's our biggest goal. There are more than 600 people who have to live with less than 40 euros a week. Families , and single mothers with 3 kids. I know a mother with 3 kids who has less than 10 euros a week and she has to do everything. There are people like these, in these kind of families. It is 600 mouths to feed. We try to make a start and give them food.

F.C: How big is the terrain?

J.M: It is 3 thousand square meters. 2100 meters which who we can count on.

F.C: Was it hard to get the space? Since it's not the country side neither the in the urban side of the city?

J.S: For starters it was a bit difficult but the most difficult part was that the government and the company who owned the grounds. So it was to do a mind change. That took the most time. But, to find the location was not the problem. The building you see right here, the same building they will build there and there as well. But, the money was gone because of the crisis in 2008, and everybody stopped building. That was fortunate for us.

F.C: Why not go in the country side? Because you would have much more terrain? Why stay here near the city?

J.M: The foods Bank is right here. So it had to do with foot miles. If we would be in the country side we wouldn't have as much people who see it and feel the need for clean and good food. What our purpose is to make everybody conscious of the fact that Groningen is the poorest city of the big cities in the Netherlands. We have to make the people conscience that there are a lot of poor people living next to you. We are keeping in mind. It has to do with the people seeing it and feel the need for clean and good food. What our purpose is that everybody conscious that Groningen is one of the poorest cities of the north. It is important to be in the city than outside.

F.C: What do you think about GMO's ?

J.M: It is a danger to the world.

F.C: Could you present yourself?

R: I am Ruth I am in between jobs this is just hobby and my goal is to meet people and charity and build a bigger network. In future year I would like to become boss of projects like these. And it's good to not be at home that is massive brain fuck. Everyone got talents and qualities and if

F.C :What motivates you to come here?

R: People are not aware were the food is coming from. GMO's are spectacular. To make people aware as well. That you can have knowledge about food you have to make food. Urban area is good as well. People are curious. Motivation. If you are altruistic and motivate and you tell you

someone else and some people say that's good or someone people just walk away. You don't need to please anyone. It's a shame that we are living countries that are poor as hell. And you have people who have a lot of food and money and they just throw it away. Neighborhood farming it has to start somewhere . you can close your eyes someday you'll be like there is n money and food. I

FC

J.M: I am idealist and a hippie. I saw too much people who were smart but had too many problems. I just went for the business. I didn't do what I liked. Is started writing. Putting in the trash can and writing. I'll give it a shot. I did a mind map and I didn't have to talk as much.

F.C: how did you start knowing how to take are

J.M: Trial and error, internet. A lot friends of mine are doing gardening. My grandfather was a farer

F.C: And you Ruth?

R:I started with gardening it wasn't about food, just trees and the garden. I am really outdoor person. I have been drawings gardens and planning and stuff. It was in a job and I was not feeling happy. I started with my balcony. And doing some square m, trial and error. Nature is difficult.

F.C: How do you see this project?

J.M: They should do it everywhere, there are some food banks...

F.C: Do you think it's part of a global movement.

J.M : In America.

R: I think it came from there Seattle and Detroit. They were the front runners.

J. M:In the people are the same there are a consciousness, people want to know where the food is coming from people are waking up at this the biggest problem is that the people are ignorant they only think about the small area around it.

R: I hope that this is not another hype. Then again when there is as start there is also an end. If someone stops they will be renewing there a lot of people who are getting conscious in this globalized thinking.

F.C :Do you think it is contributing to a public memory?

J.M: Yes

F.C: What do you think your biggest achievement is?

J.M : We are a week and half Marielle is photographing everything from the start. We are going like help with this lovely people. St

F.C: What about in the future?

J.M :I am spreading the consciousness helping their neighbors, the world becomes a etter place. We have to help each other cliché.

R: And you want to grow bigger.

J.M :we have conversation for spreading the consciousness making the city

F.C: Why only the city? And not the rural side?

J.M.: Because the rural side is for produce, is the clay is very hard to produce vegetables?

F.C :What is the relationship industrial world? Monoculture, large scale, reduction? They are in contact corporation?

J.M: Not conflicting, monoculture efficient healthy way. Not GMO way. Monoculture the most positive way if you do that healthy and controlled you cannot feed everybody with this agriculture.

R: Kind of needful in Russia everyone is producing the wrong food. They can't live from it we used to that. The western world bigger and faster. I like to think that in just 5km around you can do a lot with everyone. If everyone is aware that you don't need Monsanto and Bayer. It can be done in small scale.

J.M: small economist everything in the world is like a balloon and everything pops maybe with this as well. That's how this world works. But it must get too bug then you lose contact. They put a lot of money on how to communicate with people. You need to contain with people.

F. C: how do you feel when you work here?

J.M :It's quite stressful, because we have a horizon it's pretty nice. In every sense its positive. People are happy to work with that. It's fun to work with food,

R: We'd it with each other and that makes it grow bigger in your wings and stomach. What you can do with other people is amazing.

J.M : Everybody has something in their bags.

R. We are having good conversation and there is some conversation.

J.M: We are having a lot of philosophical discussions.

F.C: I'm done with my questions, would you like to highlight something?

J.M: But what are you going to do with all this? No... ok good luck...

